

**Defining clinical diagnosis and treatment of puerperal metritis in dairy cows: A Scoping
Review.**

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Supplemental Table S1. Signaling questions for Risk of bias assessment of the included studies on the treatment of cows with metritis (n=32). “Yes” indicates low risk of bias; “no” indicates high risk of bias; and “unclear” indicates an unclear risk of bias. If one of the relevant signaling questions is answered with “no,” this indicates high risk of bias for that specific entry.

Signaling question	Answer
1) Was the study randomized?	
*Did the investigators describe a random component in the sequence generation process	Yes/No/Unclear
2) Were the groups similar at baseline or were they adjusted for confounders in the analysis?	
*Was the distribution of relevant baseline characteristics balanced for the intervention and control groups?	Yes/No/Unclear
*If relevant, did the investigators adequately adjust for unequal distribution of some relevant baseline characteristics in the analysis?	Yes/No/Unclear
3) Were the caregivers and/or investigators blinded from knowledge which intervention each animal received during the experiment?	
*Was blinding of caregivers and investigators ensured, and was it unlikely that their blinding could have been broken?	Yes/No/Unclear
4) Was the outcome assessor blinded?	
*Was blinding of the outcome assessor ensured, and was it unlikely that blinding could have been broken?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was the outcome assessor not blinded, but do review authors judge that the outcome is not likely to be influenced by lack of blinding?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Were the personnel in charge of outcome assessment trained to perform the assessment?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was a definition of outcome described? (Treatment cure or success)	Yes/No/Unclear
5) Were incomplete outcome data adequately addressed?	
*Were all animals included in the analysis?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Were the reasons for missing outcome data unlikely to be related to true outcome? (e.g., technical failure)	Yes/No/Unclear
*Are missing outcome data balanced in numbers across intervention groups, with similar reasons for missing data across groups?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Are missing outcome data imputed using appropriate methods?	Yes/No/Unclear
6) Are reports of the study free of selective outcome reporting?	
*Was the study protocol available and were all of the study’s pre-specified primary and secondary outcomes reported in the current manuscript?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was the study protocol not available, but was it clear that the published report included all expected outcomes (i.e. comparing methods and results section)?	Yes/No/Unclear
7) Was the study apparently free of other problems that could result in high risk of bias?	
*Was the study free of contamination (pooling drugs)?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was the study free of inappropriate influence of funders?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was the study free of unit of analysis errors?	Yes/No/Unclear

*Were design-specific risks of bias absent?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Were new animals added to the control and experimental groups to replace dropouts from the original population?	Yes/No/Unclear

8) Was a clear disease definition provided?

*Was enough information for initial identification and enrollment of animals?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was a disease definition provided and followed for the identification of animals?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was initial identification of diseased animals described (diagnostic tool, definition, clinical criteria)	Yes/No/Unclear
*Were the personnel in charge of outcome assessment trained to perform the assessment?	Yes/No/Unclear
*Was a definition of outcome described? (Treatment cure or success)	Yes/No/Unclear
